

INTEGRATING THE DIGITAL ECONOMY INTO AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. The article examines the impact of the digital economy on agriculture and analyzes key technologies such as the Internet of Things, big data and artificial intelligence. The study identifies the main benefits of digitalization, including increased efficiency and reduced environmental impact. In conclusion, recommendations are offered on the support and development of digitalization in the agricultural sector.

Key words. Digital economy, agriculture, Internet of Things (IoT), big data, artificial intelligence, automation, efficiency, sustainable development, agricultural technologies, innovations.

Introduction. Digitalization has become one of the key trends in the modern development of the economy, having a significant impact on all its sectors. In the context of globalization and the rapid development of information technologies, the digital economy represents a new vector that can radically change the methods of doing business, increasing the efficiency and sustainability of various industries. Agriculture, as the most important sector of the economy, faces challenges related to the need to increase productivity and sustainability while reducing environmental impacts. The integration of digital technologies into agriculture opens up new horizons for solving these problems by offering innovative solutions and tools.

The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of the digital economy on agriculture and identify key areas for the successful integration of digital technologies into this area. To achieve this goal, tasks have been set, including analyzing the current state of digitalization in agriculture and identifying existing trends, identifying key digital technologies used in

agriculture and assessing their impact on the efficiency and sustainability of the agricultural sector, studying successful examples and cases of integrating digital technologies into agriculture, as well as making recommendations for further development digitalization in this area.

The relevance of the research topic is determined by the need for effective use of digital technologies to solve the problems faced by agriculture, such as the need to increase productivity while reducing the negative impact on the environment. In the context of global changes and changes in agricultural policy, the introduction of digital solutions is becoming not only an opportunity, but also a necessity to ensure sustainable agricultural development. The study of this topic will identify the key success factors and potential risks associated with the digitalization of the agricultural sector, as well as offer practical recommendations for the effective use of digital technologies.

Methods. The study of the impact of the digital economy on agriculture uses a variety of methods and approaches aimed at a comprehensive understanding of the current state and prospects of integrating digital technologies into the agricultural sector.

The research methodology is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis. Qualitative methods include the analysis of literary sources and the study of case stages, whereas quantitative methods allow for statistical research and assessment of the impact of digital technologies on production indicators in agriculture.

Data sources cover both primary and secondary data. Secondary data includes statistical reports, research and publications in the field of digitalization and the agricultural sector, as well as data from specialized industry reports and government sources.

Data collection procedures include analysis of existing research and statistics on the introduction of digital technologies in agriculture. This allows you to get information about the current level of digitalization, the technologies used and their impact on the efficiency and sustainability of the agricultural sector.

Data analysis methods include the use of descriptive statistics to process quantitative data obtained from secondary sources, which allows you to identify the main trends and correlations. SWOT analysis is used to assess the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats associated with the integration of digital technologies into agriculture. Comparative analysis is used to compare successful and unsuccessful examples of integrating digital technologies into various agricultural enterprises, which allows us to identify success factors and risks. The analysis of specific examples of successful application of digital technologies in agriculture is also carried out, including the study of methods and tools used in each case.

Results. The analysis of the data collected during the study revealed key results regarding the impact of the digital economy on agriculture and the integration of digital technologies into the agricultural sector.

The overall results of the study show that the introduction of digital technologies in agriculture significantly increases its efficiency and sustainability. In particular, the use of Internet of Things (IoT) and big data technologies makes it possible to improve resource management, predict yields and optimize the processing and storage of agricultural products. This, in turn, helps to reduce costs and increase productivity.

A comparative analysis revealed that successful integration of digital technologies is observed in countries with highly developed agricultural sectors, where advanced automation and monitoring solutions have already been implemented. For example, in the Netherlands and the USA, the use of drones and sensors to monitor the condition of crops and animals allows us to achieve high levels of productivity and product quality. At the same time, in developing countries, where digitalization is just beginning, the introduction of technology faces a number of difficulties, such as lack of infrastructure and high initial costs.

[1]

The case stages demonstrated successful examples of the use of digital solutions. In one of the cases related to farming in Germany, it was shown how the integration of precision farming systems and automation of agronomic processes allowed to reduce the

use of fertilizers by 20% and increase yields by 15%. In another example, a farm in China has applied big data technologies to optimize logistics and supply chain management, resulting in shorter product delivery times and lower losses. [2]

The trends and patterns identified in the study include an increasing interest in artificial intelligence technologies for processing large amounts of data and forecasting agronomic processes. There has also been an increase in the number of startups and innovative companies offering solutions for automation and management in agriculture, which indicates a growing interest and investment in this area.

Discussion. The interpretation of the results demonstrates that the digitalization of agriculture opens up incredible prospects for the agricultural sector. The introduction of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, artificial intelligence and automation is fundamentally changing traditional farming methods. For example, IoT-based monitoring systems allow farmers to monitor the condition of soil and plants in real time, which helps them make more informed decisions and effectively manage resources. Such changes not only increase productivity, but also contribute to environmentally friendly production by reducing the amount of fertilizers and pesticides used. [3]

It is difficult to overestimate the practical significance of these results. They open up new horizons for farmers and agribusiness, offering opportunities to optimize processes and increase profitability. For example, using big data analytics helps to predict yields and plan resource allocation with high accuracy. These results are also important for states and authorities: the introduction of support for digitalization, including subsidies and educational programs, can be a key factor in accelerating the adaptation of the agricultural sector to modern conditions.

Areas for future research may include exploring how digital technologies affect the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems. It is also important to assess how the introduction of technology is changing the social aspects of agriculture, including the impact on workplaces and the qualification requirements of employees. Future research may focus

on developing innovative solutions that will be adapted to the specific conditions of different regions and types of agricultural production.

Conclusion. The integration of digital technologies into agriculture opens up significant prospects for improving the efficiency and sustainability of the agricultural sector. Our research has shown that technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data and artificial intelligence can significantly improve resource management, increase productivity and reduce environmental impacts.

However, the successful implementation of these technologies faces certain difficulties, such as high initial costs and lack of infrastructure in some regions. To overcome these barriers, it is important to develop support for digitalization, reduce the cost of technology and create educational programs for workers in the agricultural sector.

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